

2023

Conference Proceedings
Egham, England

International scientific and practical Conference

MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH

Modern views and research – 2023
International scientific and practical Conference
ISBN 978-1-83853-487-5

Modern views and research – 2023
International scientific and practical Conference

Chief editor: R.Shilton

Registered Office – 71-75 Shelton Street, Covent Garden,
London, WC2H 9JQ, UK

International scientific and practical Conference

Modern views and research - 2023, May: Egham. Independent Publishing
Network Ltd.

For students, research workers

ISBN 978-1-83853-487-5

Publisher: Independent Publishing Network.

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Modern views and research - 2023

The collection of scientific papers

BONE REMODELING MARKERS AND THEIR STATE IN THE DYNAMICS OF TREATING JAW ALVEOLAR PROCESS FRACTURES USING VARIOUS IMMOBILIZATION METHODS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15001634>

Introduction. Treatment of jaw alveolar process fractures (JAPF) is a pressing issue in maxillofacial surgery. Today, in practice, immobilization using tooth-borne smooth arch bar splints is more commonly used, although they have a number of drawbacks, the most significant of which are: negative impact on periodontal tissues, a significant decrease in the level of oral hygiene and the quality of life of patients with JAPF.

Prolonged fixation of ligatures securing the splints on the teeth in the cervical area can cause the development of an inflammatory process in the periodontal tissues, and with existing chronic inflammation - its exacerbation, which significantly complicates treatment and prognosis.

In the processes of reparative regeneration, the endocrine system plays a very important role, which largely determines the rate and nature of osteogenesis. It has been established that parathyroid hormone (PTH) and cortisol have the most active effects on bone tissue metabolism. In JAPF, an increase in the content of PTH and cortisol in the blood is noted before treatment. This indicates that the stress response of the endocrine system not only does not contribute to bone regeneration but also stimulates its osteoporosis. PTH reduces the activity of osteoblasts, thereby reducing the concentration of calcitonin and osteocalcin. Increased cortisol concentration in the blood is a risk factor for the development of dental diseases or contributes to their progression.

The above provisions determined the purpose and objectives of this study, aimed at studying the level of bone metabolism markers, as well as hormones influencing calcium metabolism in the blood of patients with JAPF.

Material and methods. The following indicators were studied: levels of PTH, calcitonin; the content of bone remodeling marker - osteocalcin, and the level of cortisol in the blood of patients treated at the maxillofacial surgery clinic of the Tashkent State Dental Institute during the 2022-2023 period. Depending on the treatment method, all examined patients with JAPF were divided into 3 groups: The work is based on the experience of treating 65 patients with jaw fractures. All patients with JAPF, depending on the treatment method, were divided into the following groups: 1st group - 20 patients were treated using tooth-borne smooth arch bar splints for immobilization; 2nd group - 22 patients were treated with tooth-borne smooth arch bar splints for immobilization with the use of "Medical Herbs" (Splat) mouthwash and CALCIY TRIACTIVE® D3; 3rd group - 23 patients used dental splints fixed with composite filling materials for immobilization;

Results. As a result of the conducted research, it was established that the osteocalcin content in patients with JAPF was significantly lower than in healthy individuals ($p < 0.05$).

Biochemical blood analysis in patients with JAPF on the last day of treatment showed that in patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups, the blood osteocalcin content was still higher than in patients of the 1st group ($p < 0.01$). Along with this, in patients of the 1st group, it decreased compared to the stage before immobilization, while in the remaining three groups, there were no significant deviations from the indicated period ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusions. The study of the levels of parathyroid hormone, cortisol, calcitonin, and osteocalcin confirmed a less pronounced inflammatory reaction of the periodontal tissues and an improvement in the state of bone metabolism with gentler methods of immobilization compared to the traditional method of immobilization. Thus, with gentle immobilization, against the background of a decrease in the level of PTH and cortisol, an increase in the concentration of calcitonin and osteocalcin occurs in the dynamics of treatment. When fragments are fixed using arch bar splints, on the contrary, there is an increase in PTH and a decrease in the concentration of calcitonin and osteocalcin by the time the fixing structures are removed.

The exclusion of periodontal tissue trauma during immobilization, as well as the satisfactory state of oral hygiene, can contribute not only to a reduction in treatment complications but also to a shortening of the rehabilitation period for patients with JAPF.